

Protocol for a Retrospective Case-Case-Control Study of Cefovecin Use and Third-Generation Cephalosporin Resistance in Cats

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Background

Cefovecin is an injectable third-generation cephalosporin (3GC) antimicrobial that is frequently administered to cats. Cefpodoxime, ceftazidime, and ceftiofur are less commonly used 3GCs. Convenia® (cefovecin sodium), was approved in 2008 as a long-acting injectable antibiotic for dogs and cats [Pfizer 2008]. In cats, it is labeled for skin infections caused by susceptible strains of *Pasteurella multocida*. The label dosage is 8mg/kg of body weight, with therapeutic concentrations maintained for approximately seven days [Zoetis 2013]. It is often used for treating urinary tract infections and respiratory tract infections in cats, despite not being labeled for this indication and not being a recommended first-line treatment for these infections; first-generation cephalosporins, aminopenicillins, or other antimicrobial classes are preferred [Weese et al. 2019, Lappin et al. 2017]. Cefovecin's single-use administration may be preferable for clients who have difficulty administering medication to their cat due to patient temperament, owner disability, or lack of consistent interaction with the cat due to an indoor/outdoor lifestyle.

Cefovecin use may select for 3GC resistance, which limits treatment options for bacterial infections and can result in treatment failure and high veterinary costs. Further, this overuse of cefovecin could result in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) to first-generation cephalosporins and related aminopenicillins, which are recommended antimicrobials for common feline bacterial diseases. In Europe, cefovecin and 3GC resistance increased in bacteria isolated from companion animals over the last two decades [Marques et al. 2018, Beever et al. 2015]. Although this increase has not been solely attributed to cefovecin, which was approved by the EU in 2006 [Beever et al. 2015], cefovecin use doubled over the same period from 15% of all feline systemic AMU in the UK in 2007 [Mateus et al. 2011] to 30% in 2014 [Buckland et al. 2016]. Although cefovecin has been used to treat cats in the United States since 2008, its impact on AMR in feline pathogens and commensal bacteria is largely unknown.

Objective and Hypothesis

The objective of this study is to measure the association between prior 3GC usage and 3GC-resistant infections in cats. We expect to find that recent cefovecin use is more likely in cats with 3GC resistant infections compared to 3GC susceptible infections and uninfected cats. We will begin by evaluating this relationship among *E. coli* infections.

Study Design

This is a retrospective case-case-control study to quantify the association between cefovecin use and subsequent isolation of 3GC-resistant bacteria. A case-case-control design was selected to minimize bias and allow for the identification of risk factors for (1) both resistant and susceptible infections, (2) only resistant infections, and (3) only susceptible infections [Kaye 2005]. In a case-control study of AMR following antimicrobial use, bias is introduced by comparing resistant infections (cases) to susceptible infections (controls) because the susceptible controls do not arise from the case source population unless resistance arises from the susceptible infecting organism [Kaye 2005]. The bias may be significant for the relationship between resistance (outcome) and antimicrobial use (often the exposure of interest) because the susceptible controls are unlikely to have had recent antimicrobial exposure. If they had been treated recently with an antimicrobial, they likely would not have a subsequent susceptible culture because the pathogen would have been eliminated by the antimicrobial treatment [Kaye 2005]. The case-case-control uses both resistant and susceptible infections as cases and compares both to an uninfected control group. By comparing the risk factors identified in each case-control pairing, we can identify risk factors that are associated with the acquisition of a resistant infection [Kaye 2005]. However, this study design prohibits case-control matching, which may result in uncontrolled confounding [Kaye 2005].

Case 1: cats with 3GC-resistant *E. coli* infections

Case 2: cats with 3GC-susceptible *E. coli* infections

Controls: cats uninfected by *E. coli*

Eligible cases will be primarily identified from Cornell's Animal Health Diagnostic Laboratory records of culture and susceptibility tests. Additional cases may be identified through medical record searches at Cornell University Hospital for Animals and Cornell University Veterinary Specialists. Controls will be randomly selected from medical records.

In 2021-2022, CUHA subsidized bacterial culture and susceptibility tests, which may have increased the number of cultures performed. If cats with less severe disease were more likely to get a culture during the subsidy period than prior to 2021, this could result in a different relationship between 3GC-use and resistance. We will examine the 3GC-use and resistance relationship for 2021-2022 in a sub-analysis if possible.

Inclusion/exclusion criteria

All cats included in the study must have the following:

- Case cats: Samples that cultured *Escherichia coli* and *E. beta* and underwent antimicrobial susceptibility testing at the Animal Health Diagnostic Center at Cornell University at the Cornell Animal Health Diagnostic Laboratory after January 1, 2009
- Seen by a veterinarian (at CUHA or a referring veterinarian) between 6 months and three years prior to culture
 - For example, cats seen 3 years ago and then again at culture date are eligible
- If more than one culture was performed on a patient, the earliest culture that the patient that meets the above criteria was included in the study

In order to be categorized as Case 1, cats included must meet the following criteria:

- *E. coli* cultures with at least one third-generation cephalosporin classified as resistant or intermediate
 - Third generation cephalosporins: cefovecin, cefpodoxime, ceftazidime, ceftiofur
- Samples were classified as intermediate or resistant if they met or exceeded the following minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) breakpoints, respectively: 4 for cefovecin, 4 for cefpodoxime, 8 for ceftazidime, and 4 for ceftiofur

In order to be categorized as Case 2, cats included must meet the following criteria:

- *E. coli* cultures with all third-generation cephalosporins tested classified as susceptible
- Samples were classified as susceptible if below each of the MIC breakpoints for each 3GC

Controls:

- Did not have *E. coli* cultured. May have had other bacteria cultured or no culture at all.
- Randomly selected from cats seen at CUHA during the same time period as cases, but not matched to cases
- Meets the record time requirements (seen 3 years to 6 months prior to randomly selected control visit)

Directed Acyclic Graph

A directed acyclic graph (DAG) was created through an iterative process. Each author created a DAG identifying covariates associated with the outcome (3GC-resistant infection) and exposure (recent cefovecin use). The DAGs were compared, discussed, and combined. All authors agreed upon the final DAG, which was created in LucidChart. DAGitty (<http://www.dagitty.net/>) was

used to identify the minimal sufficient adjustment sets to estimate the total effect of the exposure on the outcome. One example of a minimal sufficient adjustment set is highlighted in red in Figure 1. The DAG was used to identify information that should be collected from cat medical records.

Figure 1: Directed acyclic graph of the relationship between recent Covenia use (exposure), 3GC-resistant infections (outcome), and covariates. Red covariates and pathways are a minimal sufficient adjustment set.

Data Collection

Data was obtained from the Animal Health Diagnostic Center at Cornell University and the Cornell University Hospital for Animals ezyVet records. Information on age, sex, breed, weight, lifestyle, vaccination, presenting complaint, hospitalization, comorbidities, concurrent medications, hospitalization, previous 3GC use, and bacterial culture results were recorded on RedCap. Data collection forms are included at the end of the protocol.

Patient record identifiers and lab accession numbers will not be exported out of RedCap.

Analysis Plan

A descriptive analysis will be performed on each variable in the entire study population and within each case or control group. Chi-squared testing, for categorical covariates, and ANOVA,

for continuous covariates, will be used to identify univariate associations between groups (case 1, case 2, controls) and covariates. Statistical significance will be evaluated at $P < 0.05$.

A multivariable logistic regression model will be created for each case-control pairing; case status will be the outcome and antimicrobial exposure will be a predictor. Potential confounders identified in the DAG or identified with the univariate testing will be included as covariates. The case 1 (resistant infection) and case 2 (susceptible infection) models will be compared [Kaye 2005]. Risk factors that are significant in both models are risk factors for *E. coli* infection in general. Risk factors that are significant in the resistant model but not the susceptible model are unique risk factors for acquiring a resistant infection.

In addition, depending on the variability in time of cefovecin exposure, we will examine the effect of time since cefovecin exposure is a potential effect modifier. We would expect more recent exposure to be a larger risk factor for a resistant infection than exposure longer ago. We can conduct a similar subanalysis of cefovecin dosage.

References

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Form 1

Form ID _____

Patient Details

EzyVet Patient ID #:

(Patient ID, not Client ID!)

Age Sex Breed Weight (kg)

____ _

Date of most recent visit at CUHA or rDVM prior to the culture date

How many total visits did this patients have in the past 6 months?

(Hospitalization episode >1 day still counts as 1 visit)

Date of oldest visit at CUHA or rDVM within 3 years of the culture.

Date of Visit for relevant culture

Hospital Service

- ER/ECC _____
- Internal Medicine _____
- Oncology _____
- Dentistry _____
- Surgery (soft tissue or orthopedic) _____
- Primary Care _____
- Dermatology _____
- Neurology _____
- Ophthalmology _____
- Other _____

(if admitted through ER but then transferred, select transfer service/primary service)

Length of Hospitalization (days)

Presenting complaint for visit that the relevant culture was performed for

(Limit to 1-3 words)

How many of the visits in the past 6 months were related to the same chief complaint that the culture was performed for?

(Hospitalization episode for >1 day still counts as 1 visit)

Concurrent Diagnoses at time of visit? (Chronic = present for 3 months or longer)

- Acute kidney failure
 - Chronic kidney disease (CKD)
 - Acute upper respiratory infection (URI)
 - Chronic URI
 - Acute ear infection
 - Chronic ear infection
 - Acute urinary tract infection (UTI)
 - Chronic UTI
 - Feline Lower Urinary Tract Disease (FLUTD)
 - Diabetes mellitus type 1
 - Diabetes mellitus type 2
 - Feline Leukemia Virus (FeLV)
 - Feline Immunodeficiency Virus (FIV)
 - Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM)
 - Hyperthyroidism
 - Cancer/Malignancies
 - Immune-mediated disease (i.e. IMHA)
 - Abscess
 - Other _____
 - None
- (Only comorbidities existing 6 months prior to culture date should be counted. ex) infection from 9 months ago does not count.)

Was the patient on any systemic or topical medications from 6 months prior to the date of the culture? If so, please fill out the supplemental Medication Form.

- Yes, and I have filled out the Medication Form
- No
(Topicals do not count)

Indoor/Outdoor Status

- Indoor
- Outdoor
- Indoor/Outdoor
- Unknown

History of bite or wound in the past 6 months?

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

Was a new antibiotic administered to the patient during the visit or while admitted PRIOR to the culture?

- Yes _____
- No _____

Vaccines

- FVRCP _____
- Rabies _____
- Feline Leukemia _____
- None reported in records
- Anecdotally recorded but no dates/durations specified

Prior Cefovecin Use in the past 6 months

- Yes (Please fill out relevant Cefovecin fields in Medication Form)
- No

Bacterial culture and susceptibility performed at AHDC?

- Yes _____
- No _____

How many total cultures were performed for this patient in the 6 months prior to this visit?

AHDC Sample Number

Sample Site

- ABS
- ANAS
- ASPN
- BACIS
- BIL
- BLDW
- BONE
- BONMR
- BRAN
- BRON
- BUL
- COL
- COLC
- CONJ
- CORN
- CSF
- DRA
- EAR
- EARC
- EARPC
- EXUD
- EYE
- FEC
- FEM
- FLABD
- FLNOS
- FLPL
- FLU
- FOOT
- FPA
- GAL
- GALL
- HAI
- HARD
- INTER
- JEJ
- JF
- LAR
- LNG
- LVR
- MAM
- MASN
- MEAR
- NAIC
- NASC
- NASCF
- NASM
- NOSE
- NPW
- ORA
- ORALS
- ORAPH
- PERG
- PHAS
- PLEU
- POOL
- PRT
- PRTF
- REC
- SKI
- SKIR
- SMI
- STOM
- SUBC
- TEARS
- TISF
- TISN
- TNG
- TOE

- TOO
- TPNC
- TPOOL
- TRA
- TW
- URB
- URI
- URICATH
- URICYST
- URIVOID
- UTE
- VAG
- VAGD
- WOUS

Bacterial Species

- Escherichia coli
- Escherichia coli (beta)
- Staphylococcus spp. _____

Bacterial Results

- Quantitative _____
- Semi-Quantitative _____

Resistance to 3rd Generation Cephalosporins

- Yes
- No
- Not cultured
(Reference Claudia's list)

Cefovecin E. coli MIC

- 8
- N/A

Cefpodoxime E. coli MIC

- 8
- = 16
- > 16
- N/A

Ceftazidime E. coli MIC

- 16
- > 64
- N/A

Ceftiofur E. coli MIC

-

Medication

Form ID

EzyVet Patient ID

()

Select all oral systemic antimicrobials prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Amikacin
- Amoxicillin
- Amoxicillin-Clavulanic acid (Clavamox)
- Azithromycin
- Cefpodoxime
- Chloramphenicol
- Clindamycin
- Doxycycline
- Enrofloxacin
- Erythromycin
- Fosfomycin
- Marbofloxacin
- Metronidazole
- Nitrofurantoin
- Orbifloxacin
- Penicillin
- Pradofloxacin
- Rifampin
- Sulfadimethoxine
- Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole
- Tylosin
- Vancomycin
- Other

Amikacin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Amoxicillin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Clavamox Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Azithromycin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Cefpodoxime Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Chloramphenicol Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Clindamycin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Doxycycline Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Enrofloxacin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Erythromycin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Fosfomycin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Marbofloxacin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Metronidazole Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Nitrofurantoin Dose (mg/kg/dose)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Orbifloxacin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Penicillin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Pradofloxacin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Rifampin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Sulfadimethoxine Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Tylosin (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Vancomycin Dose (mg/kg/day)

(indicate # of days this dose was given (ex. 10mg/kg/day for 7 days) if applicable)

Other systemic antimicrobials prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture

(Format: Name, Dose (mg/kg/day) for __ days if applicable)

Select all injectable systemic antimicrobials prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Ampicillin-sulbactam (Unasyn)
- Cefovecin (Convenia)
- Imipenem/Cilastatin (Premaxin)

Unasyn Dose (mg/kg/day)

How many doses of Unasyn was received over the 6 month period prior to the date of the culture?

Where was Cefovecin administered?

- CUHA _____
- rDVM {cefdate}
- Given per records, but no dose or date indicated

Number of Cefovecin Doses in the 6 months prior to culture

Cefovecin volume administered (mL) _____

Cefovecin dose administered (mg) _____

Cefovecin dose administered (mg/kg) _____

Was the amount of cefovecin administered an appropriate label dose? (1 = Yes, 0 = No) _____

Imipenem Dose (mg/kg/day)

How many doses of Imipenem was administered during the 6 month period prior to the date of the culture?

Select all systemic immunosuppressants prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Chlorambucil
- Cyclophosphamide
- Cyclosporine
- Dexamethasone
- Prednisolone
- Vinblastine
- Other

Name(s) of other systemic immunosuppressant medications prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture

(Format: Name, Dose (mg/kg/day) for __ days if applicable)

Select all otic medications prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Neomycin (Animax, Quadritop, Tresaderm)
- Enrofloxacin (Baytril Otic, BNT)
- Gentamicin (Mometamax, Otomax)
- Polymixin B (Surolan)
- Florfenicol (Claro, Osurnia)
- Orbifloxacin (Posatex)
- Other

Name(s) of other otic medications prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture

Select all ophthalmic medications prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Oxytetracycline (Terramycin)
- Neomycin - Polymixin B - Bacitracin (NeoPolyBac)
- Gentamicin
- Ofloxacin
- Tobramycin
- Other

Name(s) of other ophthalmic medications prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture

Select all topical skin medications prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Neomycin (Neo-Predef powder)
- Neomycin - Polymixin B - Bacitracin (NeoPolyBac)
- Neomycin (Animax, Quadritop, Tresaderm)
- Chlorhexidine (shampoos, wipes, sprays, mousse)
- Other

Other topical skin medications prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture

Select all systemic medications prescribed to the patient during the 6 month period predating the culture.

- Fluoxetine
- Gabapentin
- Meloxicam
- Methimazole
- Mirtazapine
- Robenacoxib (Onsior)
- Other

Name(s) of other systemic medications prescribed during the 6 month period prior to culture
